

A Review on SAR Imaging Techniques for Low RCS Targets

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Abstract: The method known as synthetic aperture radar (SAR) is utilized for creating high-resolution photographs stationary scenes. SAR is an imaging radar framed on a moving platform. In radar signal processing discovery of a weakly observable target is one of the most interesting area. In this survey, we will discuss about radar systems. Typical applications of radar include synthetic aperture radar, military application, airborne and spaceborne operation, speed control, air traffic control, and remote sensing. We also study about various imaging techniques that are used. Finally, potential applications of SAR imaging techniques.

Keywords: SAR, detection, observable target, imaging techniques, radar system.

1. INTRODUCTION

The electromagnetic detection technology known as RADAR, or in order to function, radio detection and ranging emits electromagnetic waves and then observing the reflected waves. Range, angle, and velocity of targets are all determined via radar. Detection shows whether or not the target is present [1]. The target could be either fixed or mobile when the target is stationary, SAR method is employed when the target is not stationary, ISAR is utilized [2]. Ranging shows the separation between the item and the RADAR. Radar can be divided into two categories both active and passive radar are used. An antenna transmits high-frequency radio waves onto the surface of the earth in active radar, which then collects information from the object's backscattered radio waves. Mono-static radars fall under this category [3-6]. The transmitter and the receptor are in the same place in this [6]. The transmitter and the receptor are located in distinct places in a passive radar system. The signal propagating from a different point is what a passive radar system relies on [7-9]. Bi-static radar is the name given to this type target with a low RCS can be manipulated remotely, uses aerodynamic forces to produce lift, and does not require a human operator [10]. The low RCS targets have more widespread uses in both the military and public spheres. Warfare and spying are just two of the many military uses for low RCS targets [11-12]. The civil applications cover things like mountain mapping and other things [13]. The region absorbing the energy that generates in all directions is referred to as the targets RCS (ρ) [14]. Low RCS target or small target refers to a target with RCS of under one square meter [15]. Due to its ability to carry explosives, an undefinable low-RCS target at the border might threaten national security by gathering important information and destroying material. An active sensor is largely responsible for finding low RCS targets [16-18].

2. RADAR SYSTEMS

Depending on the sort of signal a radar could process, the following two categories can be used to categorise radar [19].

Fig. 1 Block Diagram of Pulse Radar on High power

2.1 Pulse Radar

Radar that employs pulse signals to find stationary objects is known as the simple or fundamental pulse radar [20-22]. It uses a single antenna to broadcast and receive signals and a duplexer to do so. The antenna will transmit a pulse signal with each tick of the clock [23]. The time gap that involves the two clock pulsations must be carefully choose to ensure that the present clock pulsations associated echo signal must be obtained prior the subsequent clock pulsations, it is crucial to set the time gap between the two clock pulses [24]. Moving Targets indication Radar is the name of the radar that use pulse signal to find non-stationary objects [25]. It is also known as MTI Radar or just MTI Radar [26]. It makes use of duplexer to transmit and receive signals using a single antenna [27]. MTI Radar uses the Doppler effects hypothesis to distinguish between stationary and non-stationary objects [29].

2.2 CW Radar

The term “continuous wave radar” speaks more about a particular kind of operational radar by using a continuous signal or wave .in order to track moving targets they use the doppler effect [30-33].

Fig.2. Block Diagram of Continuous Wave Radar

It is possible to discriminate between these two CW radar types they are

2.2.1 Continuous wave radar without modulated

Unmodulated CW Radar for short, is a radar type that uses a constant signal (wave) to identify moving targets. It also goes by the name CW Doppler Radar [34]. Two antennas are needed for this radar [35]. Wherein One of these two antennas serve as a signal transmitter, second antenna is utilised in signal reception [36]. Target distance from the radar is not measured only the target's speed is measured.

2.2.2 FMCW RADAR

FMCW Radar (Linear Frequency-Modulated Continuous-Wave) is the name given to CW Doppler Radar if it employs linear frequency modulation [37-39]. It is also referred to as FMCW, or frequency-modulated continuous-wave radar [40]. Two antennas are needed for this radar. Wherein one antenna serves in signal transmission, the second antenna is utilised in signal reception [41]. Along with the target's speed, it also calculates at what distance target is from the radar [42]. Among the several types of radar, tracking radar tracks the movement of one or more targets. Before it begins the tracking activity, it typically carries out the following tasks [43-45].

- Determining the doppler frequency shift.
- Determining angle of elevation and azimuth.
- Target recognition.
- The targets range.

3. SAR TARGET DETECTION METHODS

3.1 Target Detection in Multi-static

The raw radar data that was available at the sensor's output was used for the detection [46]. The HMM's fundamental premise that samples of data may be accurately described as random processes with parameters, also it is possible to estimate the stochastic process's parameters within a clearly defined framework [47] the process of simultaneously estimating position of the target and speed utilizing a functioning radar network and maximum search. This maxima search does not require data association because it operates directly in the position-velocity space [49-52]. However, there is generally no assurance that the maxima will always match real aims. Using numerous dispersed radar systems, Feng et al [53-54] examined two non-growing characteristics in Cramer-Rao low bound target finding. They suggested a quick and effective power allocation approach for multiple cognitively dispersed radar system that heavily relies on alternating global search algorithm [55-58]. It was found that replacing one expensive high-power transmitter with multiple cheaper ones can save money without sacrificing radar performance [59] An unambiguous transmission from the transmitter and dispersed signal by surroundings both are obtained by the recipient [60]. It is possible to determine the position and velocity of any specific target by combining the data from various sensors. EL-Kamchouchy et al. suggested system architecture for multistatic s-band radar in order to locate and trace stealthy aircraft and tiny cross-sectional area aircraft [61-63]. The suggested geometrical configuration was tested with varied radar spacing in order to broaden the detection range of the air surveillance monostatic radar [64]. Also, to ascertain the improvement brought about by deploying this sort of radar, all practical stealthy aircraft paths were used to analyse the radar detection coverage [65]. The creators suggested two multistatic radar system configuration of S-band radar that would extend its detecting range of tiny covert aircraft [66]. The optimal receiver In case of a multistatic radar system is created by synthesizing target echoes with Rayleigh fluctuation and gaussian noise [67]. Baumgarten looked at how well this receiver performed and showed that under some circumstances, multistatic systems target detection skills are comparable to any of the monostatic system [68-70]. The intrinsic multistatic structures complexity may be diminished via using more direct approach, such as making a number of ancillary judgements at as many conventional receivers as feasible. A key analysis based upon an OR-criterion would then be made. In their work, D'Addio et al. found the best structures for receiving, detecting targets by centrally processing various radar data obtained from local sensors [71-72]. In-area sensors an analytical study of the model results in a unified optimum receiver for signals changing in accordance with the swerling I, II, III & IV models. Chaitanya et.al suggested a most common technique that may be used with basic DPCA cancellation in order to lessen the leftover of clutter at the output. By reducing clutter spectral breadth, the displaced phase centered antenna (DPCA) increases the likelihood of detecting slow-moving targets [73]. A

model created by Counts et al. uses calibrated measured data to exclude cable effects and direct coupling inside the system. Images created by beam formation algorithm gives a bit perception onto how well this data was acquired [74-76].

3.2 Target Detection using Multi-static Radar

In addition to the evolution of the problem with radar detection to a compound-Gaussian situation with the GLRT detection, Reddy et al. provided numerically new optimized process of a polyphase coded waveform for orthogonal MIMO radar. The Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm optimizes the transmitted orthogonal waveforms (PSO) [77]. Polarimetric radar systems send data using polarized waveforms that can mimic targets scattering patterns. The advantage of this technology can only be used to their fullest extent when the type targets is correctly identified, which can be costly [78]. Gogineni et al. presented distributed MIMO (multiple input multiple output) radar as a method for locating the target. They used a game theoretic framework for choosing a transmitting polarization by analyzing how each feasible transmit scheme would affect the different accessible target profiles [80]. This approach, unlike conventional approaches, can be put into practice without incurring significant costs because it does not need extracting the precise desired attributes from the measured data. Haungetal resolved the target estimate difficulty in bi-static multiple-input, multiple-output (MIMO) radar by using low-rank tensor completion [81]. Even though only a fraction of the data was actually recorded in the beginning across multiple pulsation intervals, the characteristics of a thin target picture, specifically the direction of arrival and direction of departure, were calculated simultaneously in this technique [82]. To retrieve the missing 3-D data, a tensor rank reduction approach based on the accelerated proximal gradient line-search (APGL) was developed [83]. The suggested techniques link the Doppler frequencies to the targets by using estimates of the target's position, velocity, and direction, either segregate or all at once [84]. The predicted Doppler frequencies at each receiver are used to calculate the number of targets in the first stage. Each target generates a unique set of Doppler frequencies for each receiver as a result of the MIMO arrangement and frequency-based nature. As a result, after a few rounds, the system can determine how many targets there are [85-87]. Particularly for high Pd values, the suggested data association algorithms can successfully match the Doppler frequencies with actual targets. Better results are obtained using the Direction Based Data Association (DBDA) method that combines a dynamic threshold (DBDA-DT) with target direction estimations [88-89]. It is crucial that these algorithms employ only two successive scans at a time rather than all previously recorded data and are independent of the goal motion parameters. Gassier et al researched and discussed the issue with moving target recognition with use of passive radar by using the DVB-T transmitters of chance in multipath environments [90]. Inconsistent correlators may be used to decrease the number of false alarms and the masking effect caused by zero Doppler contribution (ZDC) for these emissions [91].

3.3 Moving Target Detection Methods

The Discrete polynomial-phase transform (DPT) approach may be accustomed to recognize all echoes produced by an accelerating target at high SNR due to its minimal processing intricacy and excellent real-time performance. The DPT algorithm's drawback of this is because there is high mean square error of the frequency modulation rates, also a less detection probability when the SNR is low [92]. Pang et al. examined the causes of the DPT technique's performance detection degradation and presented an SDPT approach that can enhance DPT performance detection in low SNR [93]. In this technique, the segmented signal is coherently accumulated to increase the input SNR before the frequency modulation rate parameter is estimated using the DPT approach [94]. Li et. al created two novel detectors based on the Rao and Wald criteria for adaptive MIMO radar detection of moving objects in diverse settings. First, the Rao and Wald tests were created along presumption that the goal velocity and clutter structure were known. By doing a numerical optimization with respect to the desired velocity, the test variables that emerge are then modified. Finally, an estimate obtained from secondary data is used to replace the clutter structure in the adaptive versions. Finally, Monte Carlo simulations are employed to gauge how well the proposed detectors function. Gennarelli et al recommended a passive multistatic through-wall radar system for determining where moving objects are located in three-dimensional (3-D) space. The localization job is performed using an inverse source-based method, and the unidentified targets are identified to be the source of contemporary distribution produced vs their size or surface [95]. To compensate for the single frequency receiver operation's lack of resolution, a multi array picture fusion approach is used. To locate and identify animated targets in the scene, change detection is used. By lengthening the coherent integration time in airborne or spaceborne radar application, Huanget [96]. Al claim that the radars capacity to identify a weak navigational target may be increased. Coherent integration performance however, may be negatively impacted by complicated range migration (RM) and Doppler frequency migration (DFM) effects. For purpose of detecting as well as estimating the motion parameters of a weakly maneuvering target, the authors have taken into account. DFM and RM of third order [97]. A keystone transform is used as well as matching filtering process is carried out

in azimuth-time and in the range-frequency domains, to obliterate any lingering coupled outcomes among azimuth and range [98]. Finally, clear picture of an object in motion is captured, as well as three parameters- velocity, acceleration, and acceleration rate are successfully determine. In order to get a near integration performance, the computational complexity must be reduced as the reduced parameter searching dimension. Results from simulated processing are offered to verify the viability of the suggested approach [99].

3.4 Detection of ground moving Targets

A new reduced-dimensional technique for GMTI clutter avoidance using joint pixels sum-difference data was proposed by Yang et al., who worked on multi-satellite radar system. The reduced dimensional joint pixels data are obtained by orthogonally projecting the combined pixels data obtained from several synthetic aperture radar (SAR) photographs created by a multi- satellite radar system [100]. According to statistical expectations, combined into from the pixels comprise that information is shared and unique among SAR images. Afterward, adaptive processing can accomplish the GMTI and clutter cancellation goals. Onthe basis of readings from radar for airborne ground moving targets, the discriminating a set tightly spaced targets significant difficulty tracking target on the ground. Based on simulation of both single and multi-target situations, Mertens et al. incorporated the carbonized probability hypothesis density filter into the Gaussian mixture. A modified matching technique was created by Xu et al. further to enhance the shadow-aided methods detecting performance. They also tried toproduce an effective multi-feature-based shadow detection technique [101]. Additionally, the efficiency of the suggested strategy to identify moving targets for a longer period of time has been validated by the simulated tests. The findings show that the shadow-aided approach outperforms the conventionalGLRT detector in terms of detection performance [102]. It is also demonstrated that the suggested shadow-aided approach has decreased & performance of detection in the high-SNR area. Ground-penetrating radar is employed by Giannakis et al. to determine a real-time estimate contrary to its landmine signal-to-clutter ratio (SCR) identification. An example of artificial neural networks used to represent SCR in relation to the characteristics of how deep the target is, center frequency of its pulse, and the depth of the soil.

4. IMAGING ALGORITHM

Imaging Techniques in SAR are as follows:

1. The Range-Doppler algorithm.
2. Chirp-Scaling Algorithm

4.1 Range Doppler Algorithm

The findings show that the shadow-aided approach outperforms the conventional GLRT detector in terms of detection performance. It is also demonstrated that suggested shadow-aided approach has decreased performance of detection in the high-SNR area. Ground-penetrating radar is employed by Giannakis et al. to determine the real-time estimate of its landmine signal-to-clutter ratio (SCR) identification. Simulated neural networks are used to represent SCR in relation to the characteristics how deep the target is, the depth of the soil, and the pulse's frequency in the Centre [103-105]. The most crucial component of this algorithm is RCMC. Range frequency and azimuth frequency domains are used for RCMC. It is knownas the Range Doppler Algorithm because azimuth frequency is impacted using the Doppler Effect or is linked to Doppler frequency. Three alternative approaches can be used to implement RDA [106]. However, they are all comparable in steps and only differently compress secondary range (SRC) RDA's primarysteps are:

1. First range compression
2. FFT for Azimuth
3. RCMC
4. Filtering by Azimuth
5. Reverse FFT
6. Image Synthesis

The most popular SAR processing technique that offers results with a respectable level of accuracy is the implementation range doppler algorithm [108].

RDA consists of these three steps:

1. Compression of the range
2. Correction of Range cell migration
3. Compression in the azimuth.

However, the specific steps required to implement the algorithm's code are as follows:

1. Specifying auxiliary information and parameters.
2. Data transformation to 2D frequency domain
3. Implementing a Match filter and Range Compression
4. Correcting Range Cell Migration
5. Transforming Range-Doppler domain from Range-Compressed data
6. Creating a Match filter and applying Azimuth compression
7. Sending data back to the time-domain
8. Results visualization.

Fig. 3 A Processed and Improved Scene by employing RDA

4.2 Chirp-Scaling-Algorithm.

Chirp-Scaling Algorithm is abbreviated as CSA. It operates on the scaling principle where a chirp-encoded signal is subjected to frequency modulation induce the scaling or shifting of a signal, it was created expressly to replace the RCMC's interpolator [109]. The range migration of each target trajectory is compensated using chirp scaling, which employs a phase multiply. This approach holds the advantage of making the SRC dependent on azimuth frequency because the availability of the data is in the two-dimensional frequency domain [110]. The CSA's steps are:

1. Data is transformed to the range Doppler domain using azimuth FFT.
2. Using the Chirp Scaling
3. Data is transformed into a two-dimensional frequency domain using a Range FFT.
4. A phase multiply simultaneously uses RCMC, secondary range compression, and rangecompression.
5. Range IFFT that provides information in the range Doppler domain
6. A further phase multiplication uses a range-dependent matching filter to provide azimuthcompression.
7. Azimuth IFFT that returns data to the azimuth time domain is number seven.

5. SAR IMAGING MODES

There are numerous different imaging modes supported by the most recent SAR systems in addition to the simpler strip-map imaging mode that was previously provided. The antenna is separated into many sub-apertures to support these imaging modalities [111-113]. Each sub-phase apertures and amplitude can be adjusted, which alters the antenna radiation pattern and, in turn, the illuminated area.

1. Strip-Map SAR.
2. Scan SAR
3. Spotlight SAR
4. High-Resolution Wide-Swath Imaging.

5.1 Strip-Map SAR

The strip-map SAR, which has been addressed in the previous sections, is the most common configuration. In this imaging mode the antenna patterns remain fixed and it illuminates a fixed swath as shown in Fig.4. The data acquisition occurs for a continuous strip of the terrain [114-115].

Fig. 4. Strip-Map SAR Imaging Mode

5.2 Scan SAR

The Scan SAR imaging mode is used when a wider swath is required. The Antenna pattern is steered in elevation during the data acquisition interval [116]. This leads the illumination of several sub-swaths as illustrated in Fig. 5 Since each sub-swath is illuminated during a fraction of time

When compared with the strip-map situation, the azimuth resolution is proportionally degraded [117].

Fig. 5 Scan SAR Mode Increases the Swath Width at Expenses of Expenses of Azimuth Resolution.

5.3 Spotlight SAR

For a specific target region, the spotlight SAR imaging setup is employed to attain the best resolution as shown in Fig. 6. Increasing the integration time improves the resolution. In contrast to strip-map SAR operation, the antenna pattern is guided to illuminate a fixed region of interest for a significantly longer period of time. The decrease in photographing a continuous swath along [118-119].

Fig. 6 Spotlight Mode: Increases the Azimuth Resolution having as Trade-off the Decreases of the swath

5.4 High- Resolution Wide-Swath Imaging

A unique imaging technique has been suggested to get over the trade-off restriction between azimuth resolution and spatial coverage. In this imaging technique, multiple apertures recording in azimuth is combined with digital beamforming on receive in elevation. With this approach it is also getting excellent as illustrated in Fig. 7. Simultaneously Improves Azimuth Resolution and Swath Width at Expenses of Hardware and Computational Complexity. The drawback of Conventional SAR system is that they can only accomplish a large area at lower azimuth resolution. The relatively high Doppler centroid, which is one of the most critical factors that must be determined in order to compute SAR pictures is potential downside of multichannel Scan SAR approaches.

Fig. 7 High-Resolution Wide-Swath SAR

6. POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS OF SAR

Agriculture: Surface roughness variations are a sign of crop harvesting, soil tillage, and fieldploughing [123].

Floods: Surface reflection variations can be used to differentiate between heavy and minor flooding, metropolitan areas, and permanent bodies of water [124].

Land subsidence: it can be detected by differences in measurements over time, such as sinking ground brought on by the extraction of subterranean natural resource [125].

Snow cover: By identifying wet, dry, and snow-free locations, variations in surface reflection can be used to forecast snowmelt [126].

Wildfires: Penetrating dense smoke can deliver more precise and fast information about the scope of a forest fire and help assess vegetation damage [127].

Wetlands: Where land is covered by shallow water, penetration through wetland areas might disclose flooded plants [128].

7. LIMITATION AND SCOPE OF SAR

The strategies presented here can be used to find a target in a variety of circumstances. Additionally, it explains how various radar configurations can improve a target's detectability [129-132]. The majority of the methods increase computing complexity cubically as the number of transmitters increases, whereas they increase an NP problem's calculation volume exponentially [133-135]. The majority of the current radar algorithms replicate the environment (clutter) by assuming that it is stationary [136-137]. However, depending on the context in which a radar is operated, the clutter's properties might really change greatly. The performance of the radar could be severely hampered if this non-stationary fluctuation is not considered [138-141]. Since they rise only a few meters above the water's surface, small targets (such as small icebergs) are typically difficult for marine radar systems to detect [142-146]. Given that the typical RCS is low at surface marine debris, very high-resolution marine radars have the potential to detect incredibly small targets [147-150]. The statistical features of marine debris change from being uncorrelated and Gaussian to correlated and strongly tailed, which is a significant negative [151]. When a target is far away, it is frequently noticed that some algorithms cannot differentiate the shape of the target [152].

8. CONCLUSION

The numerous target detection methods are discussed in this paper, along with their many benefits and uses. Numerous researchers have used many methods to try to tackle this issue using various strategies, but some other above techniques still have significant drawbacks, which are examined and signify the study field where a solution has not yet been found.

REFERENCES

- [1] Abad RJ, Ierkic MH, Ortiz-Rivera EI. Basic understanding of cognitive radar. In 2016 IEEE ANDESCON 2016 Oct 19 (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- [2] Bergin JS, Guerci JR, Guerci RM, Rangaswamy M. MIMO clutter discrete probing for cognitive radar. In 2015 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarCon) 2015 May 10 (pp. 1666-1670). IEEE.
- [3] Zhou C, Qian W. Cognitive theory applied to radar system. In Proceedings of 2014 International Conference on Cloud Computing and Internet of Things 2014 Dec 13 (pp. 157-160). IEEE.
- [4] Haykin S. Cognitive radar: a way of the future. IEEE signal processing magazine. 2006 Feb 13;23(1):30-40.
- [5] Garg U, Raj AB, Ray KP. Cognitive Radar Assisted Target Tracking: A Study. In 2018 3rd International Conference on Communication and Electronics Systems (ICCES) 2018 Oct 15 (pp. 427-430). IEEE.
- [6] Quan S, Qian W, Guo J, Zhang Y. Cognitive radar: Critical techniques and limits. In 2014 12th International Conference on Signal Processing (ICSP) 2014 Oct 19 (pp. 2035-2038). IEEE.
- [7] Zhang T, Xia Z, Yang Y, Zhao Z, Liu X, Zhang Y, Liu D, Yin X. Waveform Optimization of High SNR and High Resolution Cognitive Radar for Sparse Target Detection. In 2021 IEEE 4th International Conference on Electronics Technology (ICET) 2021 May 7 (pp. 200-203). IEEE.
- [8] Wang L, Wang HB, Chen MY. Cognitive radar waveform design for multiple targets based on information theory. In 2016 CIE International Conference on Radar (RADAR) 2016 Oct 10 (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- [9] Badiger B, Rakesh KS, Sowmya M, Roja RB. Design and simulation of the cognitive radar for extended target using MATLAB. In 2017 2nd IEEE International Conference on Recent Trends in Electronics, Information & Communication Technology (RTEICT) 2017 May 19 (pp. 2217-2221). IEEE.
- [10] Turso S, Bertuch T, Brüggewirth S, Danklmayer A, Knott P. Electronically steered cognitive weather radar-a technology perspective. In 2017 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarConf) 2017 May 8 (pp. 0563-0566). IEEE.
- [11] Haykin S, Xue Y, Setoodeh P. Cognitive radar: Step toward bridging the gap between neuroscience and engineering. Proceedings of the IEEE. 2012 Jul 31;100(11):3102-30.

- [12] Zhang Z, Salous S, Zhu J, Song D. A novel waveform selection method for cognitive radar during target tracking based on the wind driven optimization technique. In IET International Radar Conference 2015 2015 Oct 14 (pp. 1-8). IET.
- [13] Chakraborty M, Kumawat HC, Dhavale SV. Application of DNN for radar micro-doppler signature-based human suspicious activity recognition. Pattern Recognition Letters. 2022 Oct 1;162:1-6.
- [14] Kumawat HC, Chakraborty M, Raj AA. DIAT-RadSATNet—A Novel Lightweight DCNN Architecture for Micro-Doppler-Based Small Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (SUAV) Targets' Detection and Classification. IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement. 2022 Jul 4;71:1-1.
- [15] Chakraborty M, Kumawat HC, Dhavale SV. DIAT-RadHARNet: A Lightweight DCNN for Radar Based Classification of Human Suspicious Activities. IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement. 2022 Feb 25;71:1-0.
- [16] Chakraborty M, Kumawat HC, Dhavale SV, Raj AA. DIAT- μ RadHAR (Micro-Doppler Signature Dataset) & μ RadNet (A Lightweight DCNN)—For Human Suspicious Activity Recognition. IEEE Sensors Journal. 2022 Feb 16;22(7):6851-8.
- [17] Kumawat HC, Raj AA. SP-WVD with Adaptive-Filter-Bank-Supported RF Sensor for Low RCS Targets' Nonlinear Micro-Doppler Signature/Pattern Imaging System. Sensors. 2022 Feb 4;22(3):1186.
- [18] Bhagat BB, Raj AB. Detection of human presence using UWB radar. In 2021 International Conference on System, Computation, Automation and Networking (ICSCAN) 2021 Jul 30 (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [19] Tirumalesh K, Raj AB. Laboratory based automotive radar for mobile targets ranging. In 2021 International Conference on System, Computation, Automation and Networking (ICSCAN) 2021 Jul 30 (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [20] Rathor SB, Dayalan S, Raj AB. Digital implementation of radar receiver and signal processing algorithms. In 2021 International Conference on System, Computation, Automation and Networking (ICSCAN) 2021 Jul 30 (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [21] Sai KH, Raj AB. Deep CNN supported recognition of ship using SAR images in maritime environment. In 2021 International Conference on System, Computation, Automation and Networking (ICSCAN) 2021 Jul 30 (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- [22] Kumawat HC, Chakraborty M, Raj AA, Dhavale SV. DIAT- μ SAT: Small aerial targets' micro-Doppler signatures and their classification using CNN. IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters. 2021 Aug 10;19:1-5.
- [23] Upadhyay M, Murthy SK, Raj AB. Intelligent System for Real time detection and classification of Aerial Targets using CNN. In 2021 5th International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems (ICICCS) 2021 May 6 (pp. 1676-1681). IEEE.
- [24] Akella AS, Raj AB. DCNN based activity classification of ornithopter using radar micro-Doppler images. In 2021 5th International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems (ICICCS) 2021 May 6 (pp. 780-784). IEEE.
- [25] Singh U, Raj AB. A comparative study of multiple radar waveform design techniques. In 2020 Second International Conference on Inventive Research in Computing Applications (ICIRCA) 2020 Jul 15 (pp. 1177-1182). IEEE.
- [26] Sharma G, Raj AB. Effects of antenna radiation pattern on airborne sar imaging with sufficient cyclic prefix-ofdm. In 2020 IEEE 4th Conference on Information & Communication Technology (CICT) 2020 Dec 3 (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [27] Raut A, Raj AB. Signal processing for digital beamforming on transmit in mimo radar. In 2020 Second International Conference on Inventive Research in Computing Applications (ICIRCA) 2020 Jul 15 (pp. 1106-1111). IEEE.
- [28] De S, Elayaperumal S, Raj AB. Angle estimation using modified subarray level monopulse ratio algorithm and s-curve in digital phased array radar. In 2020 Second International Conference on Inventive Research in Computing Applications (ICIRCA) 2020 Jul 15 (pp. 936-941). IEEE.

- [29] Mazumder J, Raj AB. Detection and classification of UAV using propeller Doppler profiles for counter UAV systems. In 2020 5th International Conference on Communication and Electronics Systems (ICCES) 2020 Jun 10 (pp. 221-227). IEEE.
- [30] Kumawat HC, Raj AB. Approaching/receding target detection using cw radar. In 2020 5th International Conference on Communication and Electronics Systems (ICCES) 2020 Jun 10 (pp. 136-141). IEEE.
- [31] Singh U, Raj AB. A Comparison Study of Multiple Radar Waveform Design Techniques. In Customised floating-point algorithm for the ranging systems", IEEE Inter., Conf., " Systems Inventive Research in Computing Applications (ICIRCA 2020)" 2020 (pp. 1-7).
- [32] Phanindra BR, Pralhad RN, Raj AB. Machine learning based classification of ducted and non-ducted propeller type quadcopter. In 2020 6th International Conference on Advanced Computing and Communication Systems (ICACCS) 2020 Mar 6 (pp. 1296-1301). IEEE.
- [33] Kumawat HC, Raj AB. Moving target detection in foliage environment using FMCW radar. In 2020 5th International Conference on Communication and Electronics Systems (ICCES) 2020 Jun 10 (pp. 418-421). IEEE.
- [34] Anju P, Raj AB, Shekhar C. Pulse Doppler Processing-A Novel Digital Technique. In 2020 4th International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems (ICICCS) 2020 May 13 (pp. 1089-1095). IEEE.
- [35] Behera DK, Raj AB. Drone detection and classification using deep learning. In 2020 4th International Conference on Intelligent Computing and Control Systems (ICICCS) 2020 May 13 (pp. 1012-1016). IEEE.
- [36] Raj AA, Kumawat HC. Extraction of Doppler Signature of micro-to-macro rotations/motions using CW Radar assisted measurement system. IET-Science, Measurement & Technology. 2020 Mar.
- [37] Rajkumar C, Raj AB. Design and Development of DSP Interfaces and Algorithm for FMCW Radar Altimeter. In 2019 4th International Conference on Recent Trends on Electronics, Information, Communication & Technology (RTEICT) 2019 May 17 (pp. 720-725). IEEE.
- [38] Kumawat HC, Raj AB. Data acquisition and signal processing system for CW Radar. In 2019 5th International Conference On Computing, Communication, Control And Automation (ICCUBEA) 2019 Sep 19 (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- [39] Shakya P, Raj AB. Inverse Synthetic Aperture Radar Imaging Using Fourier Transform Technique. In 2019 1st International Conference on Innovations in Information and Communication Technology (ICIICT) 2019 Apr 25 (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- [40] Gupta D, Raj AB, Kulkarni A. Multi-Bit Digital Receiver Design For Radar Signature Estimation. In 2018 3rd IEEE International Conference on Recent Trends in Electronics, Information & Communication Technology (RTEICT) 2018 May 18 (pp. 1072-1075). IEEE.
- [41] Garg U, Raj AB, Ray KP. Cognitive Radar Assisted Target Tracking: A Study. In 2018 3rd International Conference on Communication and Electronics Systems (ICCES) 2018 Oct 15 (pp. 427-430). IEEE.
- [42] Akhter N, Kumawat HC, ArockiaBazil Raj A. Development of RF-Photonic System for Automatic Targets' Nonlinear Rotational/Flapping/Gliding Signatures Imaging Applications. Journal of Circuits, Systems and Computers. 2022 Dec 2:2350131.
- [43] Akhter N, Kumawat HC, ArockiaBazil Raj A. Development of RF-Photonic System for Automatic Targets' Nonlinear Rotational/Flapping/Gliding Signatures Imaging Applications. Journal of Circuits, Systems and Computers. 2022 Dec 2:2350131.
- [44] De S, Raj AB. Modelling of dual-band (S-band and X-band) RF-Photonics radar system in Opti-system environment. In 2022 8th International Conference on Advanced Computing and Communication Systems (ICACCS) 2022 Mar 25 (Vol. 1, pp. 310-315). IEEE.
- [45] De S, Bazil Raj AA. A survey on photonics technologies for radar applications. Journal of Optics. 2022 Jun 25:1-30.

- [46] Kumar S, Raj AB. Design of X-band FMCW radar using digital Doppler processor. In2021 International Conference on System, Computation, Automation and Networking (ICSCAN) 2021 Jul 30 (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- [47] Akhter N, Kumawat HC, ArockiaBazil Raj A. Development of RF-Photonic System for Automatic Targets' Nonlinear Rotational/Flapping/Gliding Signatures Imaging Applications. Journal of Circuits, Systems and Computers. 2022 Dec 2:2350131.
- [48] Rana A, Raj AB. Non-linear orbital path tracking of ornithopters. In2021 International Conference on System, Computation, Automation and Networking (ICSCAN) 2021 Jul 30 (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [49] Pramod A, Shankaranarayanan H, Raj AA. A Precision Airdrop System for Cargo Loads Delivery Applications. In2021 International Conference on System, Computation, Automation and Networking (ICSCAN) 2021 Jul 30 (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- [50] Raj AB. Tunable Dual-Band RF Exciter-Receiver Design For Realizing Photonics Radar. In2021 International Conference on System, Computation, Automation and Networking (ICSCAN) 2021 Jul 30 (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- [51] Yadav N, Raj AR. Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing Waveform Based Radar System. In2021 International Conference on System, Computation, Automation and Networking (ICSCAN) 2021 Jul 30 (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- [52] Rao MK, Raj AB. Reduced radar cross-section target imaging system. In2021 International Conference on System, Computation, Automation and Networking (ICSCAN) 2021 Jul 30 (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [53] Magisetty R, Raj AB, Datar S, Shukla A, Kandasubramanian B. Nanocomposite engineered carbon fabric-mat as a passive metamaterial for stealth application. Journal of Alloys and Compounds. 2020 Dec 25;848:155771.
- [54] Mohan A, Raj AB. Array thinning of beamformers using simple genetic algorithm. In2020 International Conference on Computational Intelligence for Smart Power System and Sustainable Energy (CISPSSE) 2020 Jul 29 (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- [55] Maddegalla M, Raj AA, Rao GS. Beam steering and control algorithm for 5-18ghz transmit/receive module based active planar array. In2020 International Conference on System, Computation, Automation and Networking (ICSCAN) 2020 Jul 3 (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [56] Singh N, Raj AB. Estimation of Heart Rate and Respiratory Rate using Imaging Photoplethysmography Technique. In2020 International Conference on System, Computation, Automation and Networking (ICSCAN) 2020 Jul 3 (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- [57] Gunjal MM, Raj AB. Improved direction of arrival estimation using modified MUSIC algorithm. In2020 5th International Conference on Communication and Electronics Systems (ICCES) 2020 Jun 10 (pp. 249-254). IEEE.
- [58] Thiruvoth DV, Raj AB, Kumar BP, Kumar VS, Gupta RD. Dual-band shared-aperture reflectarray antenna element at Ku-band for the TT&C application of a geostationary satellite. In2019 4th International Conference on Recent Trends on Electronics, Information, Communication & Technology (RTEICT) 2019 May 17 (pp. 361-364). IEEE.
- [59] Gupta A, Rai AB. Feature extraction of intra-pulse modulated LPI waveforms using STFT. In2019 4th International Conference on Recent Trends on Electronics, Information, Communication & Technology (RTEICT) 2019 May 17 (pp. 742-746). IEEE.
- [60] Vaishnavi R, Unnikrishnan G, Raj AB. Implementation of algorithms for Point target detection and tracking in Infrared image sequences. In2019 4th International Conference on Recent Trends on Electronics, Information, Communication & Technology (RTEICT) 2019 May 17 (pp. 904-909). IEEE.
- [61] Gite TY, Pradeep PG, Raj AB. Design and evaluation of c-band FMCW radar system. In2018 2nd International Conference on Trends in Electronics and Informatics (ICOEI) 2018 May 11 (pp. 1274-1276). IEEE.
- [62] Meyer-Baese U, Meyer-Baese U. Digital signal processing with field programmable gate arrays. Berlin: springer; 2007 Apr
- [63] Kitcher P. The division of cognitive labor. The journal of philosophy. 1990 Jan 1;87(1):5-22.

- [64] Cheeran AN, Prathibha A, Priyarenjini AR, Nirmal AV, Raj AB, Patki AB, Syed AH, Sinha A, Abhijith HV, Patil AA, Chalwadi AD. 2019 IEEE International Conference on Recent Trends on Electronics, Information & Communication Technology (RTEICT-2019).
- [65] Srihari BR, Panakkal VP, Raj AB. A Modified Track-Oriented Multiple Hypothesis Tracking Approach for Coastal Surveillance.
- [66] ArockiaBazil Raj A, Arputha Vijaya Selvi J, Kumar D. Sivakumaran, N 2014, 'Mitigation of Beam Fluctuation due to Atmospheric Turbulence and Prediction of Control Quality using Intelligent Decision-Making Tools'. Applied optics.;53(17):37962-806.
- [67] Srivastva R, Raj A, Patnaik T, Kumar B. A survey on techniques of separation of machine printed text and handwritten text. International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology. 2013 Feb;2(3):552-5.
- [68] ArockiaBazil Raj A, Selvi JA, Raghavan S. Real-time measurement of meteorological parameters for estimating low-altitude atmospheric turbulence strength (Cn2). IET Science, Measurement & Technology. 2014 Nov;8(6):459-69.
- [69] Pasupathi TA, Bazil Raj AA, Arputhavijayaselvi J. FPGA IMPLEMENTATION OF ADAPTIVE INTEGRATED SPIKING NEURAL NETWORK FOR EFFICIENT IMAGE RECOGNITION SYSTEM. ICTACT Journal on Image & Video Processing. 2014 May 1;4(4).
- [70] Raj AA, Selvi JA, Kumar D, Sivakumaran N. Mitigation of beam fluctuation due to atmospheric turbulence and prediction of control quality using intelligent decision-making tools. Applied optics. 2014 Jun 10;53(17):3796-806.
- [71] Bazil Raj AA, Vijaya Selvi AJ, Durai KD, Singaravelu RS. Intensity feedback-based beam wandering mitigation in free-space optical communication using neural control technique. EURASIP Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking. 2014 Dec;2014(1):1-8.
- [72] Srihari BR, Panakkal VP, Raj AB. A Modified Track-Oriented Multiple Hypothesis Tracking Approach for Coastal Surveillance.
- [73] Kumawat HC, Samczyński P. Spectrum Localization and Hough Transform-Based β Tuning for LSS Targets' Accurate Micro-Doppler Imaging System. IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurement. 2022 Jul 5;71:1-1.
- [74] Sharma G, Raj AA. Low Complexity Interference Mitigation Technique in IRCI-free SAR Imaging Algorithms. IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters. 2022 Apr 29.
- [75] Bell KL, Baker CJ, Smith GE, Johnson JT, Rangaswamy M. Cognitive radar framework for target detection and tracking. IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Signal Processing. 2015 Aug 6;9(8):1427-39.
- [76] Smith GE, Cammenga Z, Mitchell A, Bell KL, Johnson J, Rangaswamy M, Baker C. Experiments with cognitive radar. IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine. 2016 Dec;31(12):34-46.
- [77] Martone AF. Cognitive radar demystified. URSI Radio Science Bulletin. 2014 Sep;2014(350):10-22.
- [78] Guerci JR. Cognitive radar: A knowledge-aided fully adaptive approach. In 2010 IEEE Radar Conference 2010 May 10 (pp. 1365-1370). IEEE.
- [79] Haykin S. Cognitive radar networks. In Fourth IEEE Workshop on Sensor Array and Multichannel Processing, 2006. 2006 Jul 12 (pp. 1-24). IEEE.
- [80] Charlish A, Hoffmann F, Klemm R, Nickel U, Gierull C. Cognitive radar management. Novel Radar Techniques and Applications. 2017 Oct 23;2:157-93.
- [81] Li X, Fan MM. Research advance on cognitive radar and its key technology. Acta Electronica Sinica. 2012 Sep 25;40(9):1863.
- [82] Wicks M. Spectrum crowding and cognitive radar. In 2010 2nd International Workshop on Cognitive Information Processing 2010 Jun 14 (pp. 452-457). IEEE.

- [83] Chavali P, Nehorai A. Scheduling and power allocation in a cognitive radar network for multiple-target tracking. *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*. 2011 Dec 6;60(2):715-29.
- [84] Elbir AM, Mishra KV, Eldar YC. Cognitive radar antenna selection via deep learning. *IET Radar, Sonar & Navigation*. 2019 Jun;13(6):871-80.
- [85] Horne C, Ritchie M, Griffiths H. Proposed ontology for cognitive radar systems. *IET Radar, Sonar & Navigation*. 2018 Dec;12(12):1363-70.
- [86] Bell KL, Johnson JT, Smith GE, Baker CJ, Rangaswamy M. Cognitive radar for target tracking using a software defined radar system. In 2015 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarCon) 2015 May 10 (pp. 1394-1399). IEEE.
- [87] Brüggewirth S, Warnke M, Wagner S, Barth K. Cognitive radar for classification. *IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine*. 2019 Dec 1;34(12):30-8.
- [88] Martone AF, Sherbondy KD, Kovarskiy JA, Kirk BH, Owen JW, Ravenscroft B, Egbert A, Goad A, Dockendorf A, Thornton CE, Buehrer RM. Practical aspects of cognitive radar. In 2020 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarConf20) 2020 Sep 21 (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [89] Smits F, Huizing A, van Rossum W, Hiemstra P. A cognitive radar network: Architecture and application to multiplatform radar management. In 2008 European Radar Conference 2008 Oct 30 (pp. 312-315). IEEE.
- [90] Greco MS, Gini F, Stinco P, Bell K. Cognitive radars: On the road to reality: Progress thus far and possibilities for the future. *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*. 2018 Jun 27;35(4):112-25.
- [91] Metcalf J, Blunt SD, Himed B. A machine learning approach to cognitive radar detection. In 2015 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarCon) 2015 May 10 (pp. 1405-1411). IEEE.
- [92] Charlish A, Hoffmann F, Degen C, Schlangen I. The development from adaptive to cognitive radar resource management. *IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine*. 2020 Jun 1;35(6):8-19.
- [93] Ender J, Brüggewirth S. Cognitive radar-enabling techniques for next generation radar systems. In 2015 16th International Radar Symposium (IRS) 2015 Jun 24 (pp. 3-12). IEEE.
- [94] Aubry A, De Maio A, Jiang B, Zhang S. Ambiguity function shaping for cognitive radar via complex quartic optimization. *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*. 2013 Jul 18;61(22):5603-19.
- [95] Charlish A, Hoffmann F. Anticipation in cognitive radar using stochastic control. In 2015 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarCon) 2015 May 10 (pp. 1692-1697). IEEE.
- [96] Mishra KV, Eldar YC. Performance of time delay estimation in a cognitive radar. In 2017 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP) 2017 Mar 5 (pp. 3141-3145). IEEE.
- [97] Martone AF, Sherbondy KD, Kovarskiy JA, Kirk BH, Narayanan RM, Thornton CE, Buehrer RM, Owen JW, Ravenscroft B, Blunt S, Egbert A. Closing the loop on cognitive radar for spectrum sharing. *IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine*. 2021 Sep 9;36(9):44-55.
- [98] Kozy M, Yu J, Buehrer RM, Martone A, Sherbondy K. Applying deep-Q networks to target tracking to improve cognitive radar. In 2019 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarConf) 2019 Apr 22 (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [99] Baylis C, Fellows M, Cohen L, Marks II RJ. Solving the spectrum crisis: Intelligent, reconfigurable microwave transmitter amplifiers for cognitive radar. *IEEE Microwave Magazine*. 2014 Jul 9;15(5):94-107.
- [100] Guerci JR. Cognitive radar: The next radar wave?. *Microwave Journal*. 2011 Jan 1;54(1).
- [101] Aubry A, De Maio A, Piezzo M, Naghsh MM, Soltanalian M, Stoica P. Cognitive radar waveform design for spectral coexistence in signal-dependent interference. In 2014 IEEE Radar Conference 2014 May 19 (pp. 0474-0478). IEEE.
- [102] Selvi E, Buehrer RM, Martone A, Sherbondy K. On the use of Markov decision processes in cognitive radar: An application to target tracking. In 2018 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarConf18) 2018 Apr 23 (pp. 0537-0542). IEEE.
- [103] Zhang X, Cui C. Signal detection for cognitive radar. *Electronics Letters*. 2013 Apr;49(8):559-60.

- [104] Shaghghi M, Adve RS. Machine learning based cognitive radar resource management. In2018 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarConf18) 2018 Apr 23 (pp. 1433-1438). IEEE.
- [105] Kirk BH, Narayanan RM, Gallagher KA, Martone AF, Sherbondy KD. Avoidance of time-varying radio frequency interference with software-defined cognitive radar. IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems. 2018 Dec 13;55(3):1090-107.
- [106] Romero RA, Goodman NA. Cognitive radar network: Cooperative adaptive beamsteering for integrated search-and-track application. IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems. 2013 Apr 5;49(2):915-31.
- [107] Mitchell AE, Smith GE, Bell KL, Rangaswamy M. Single target tracking with distributed cognitive radar. In2017 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarConf) 2017 May 8 (pp. 0285-0288). IEEE.
- [108] Wu L, Babu P, Palomar DP. Cognitive radar-based sequence design via SINR maximization. IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing. 2016 Oct 26;65(3):779-93.
- [109] Kang L, Bo J, Hongwei L, Siyuan L. Reinforcement learning based anti-jamming frequency hopping strategies design for cognitive radar. In2018 IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing, Communications and Computing (ICSPCC) 2018 Sep 14 (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- [110] Aubry A, Carotenuto V, De Maio A, Govoni MA. Multi-snapshot spectrum sensing for cognitive radar via block-sparsity exploitation. IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing. 2018 Dec 13;67(6):1396-406.
- [111] Nijssure Y, Chen Y, Boussakta S, Yuen C, Chew YH, Ding Z. Novel system architecture and waveform design for cognitive radar radio networks. IEEE transactions on vehicular technology. 2012 Jun 6;61(8):3630-42.
- [112] Carotenuto V, Aubry A, De Maio A, Pasquino N, Farina A. Assessing agile spectrum management for cognitive radar on measured data. IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine. 2020 Jun 1;35(6):20-32.
- [113] Chen P, Qi C, Wu L, Wang X. Estimation of extended targets based on compressed sensing in cognitive radar system. IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology. 2016 May 10;66(2):941-51.
- [114] Chavali P, Nehorai A. Cognitive radar for target tracking in multipath scenarios. In2010 International Waveform Diversity and Design Conference 2010 Aug 8 (pp. 000110-000114). IEEE.
- [115] Bockmair M, Fischer C, Letsche-Nuesseler M, Neumann C, Schikorr M, Steck M. Cognitive radar principles for defence and security applications. IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine. 2019 Dec 1;34(12):20-9.
- [116] Martone AF, Charlish A. Cognitive radar for waveform diversity utilization. In2021 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarConf21) 2021 May 7 (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [117] Oechslin R, Aulenbacher U, Rech K, Hinrichsen S, Wieland S, Wellig P. Cognitive radar experiments with CODIR. InInternational Conference on Radar Systems (Radar 2017) 2017 Oct 23 (pp. 1-6). IET.
- [118] Inggs M. Passive coherent location as cognitive radar. In2009 International Waveform Diversity and Design Conference 2009 Feb 8 (pp. 229-233). IEEE.
- [119] Huizing A, Heiligers M, Dekker B, de Wit J, Cifola L, Harmanny R. Deep learning for classification of mini-UAVs using micro-Doppler spectrograms in cognitive radar. IEEE Aerospace and Electronic Systems Magazine. 2019 Nov 8;34(11):46-56.
- [120] Stinco P, Greco M, Gini F, Himed B. Channel parameters estimation for cognitive radar systems. In2014 4th International Workshop on Cognitive Information Processing (CIP) 2014 May 26 (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [121] Pattanayak K, Krishnamurthy V, Berry C. How can a Cognitive Radar Mask its Cognition?. InICASSP 2022-2022 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP) 2022 May 23 (pp. 5897-5901). IEEE.
- [122] Stinco P, Greco MS, Gini F. Spectrum sensing and sharing for cognitive radars. IET Radar, Sonar & Navigation. 2016 Mar;10(3):595-602.

- [123] Kovarskiy JA, Owen JW, Narayanan RM, Blunt SD, Martone AF, Sherbondy KD. Spectral prediction and notching of RF emitters for cognitive radar coexistence. In2020 IEEE International Radar Conference (RADAR) 2020 Apr 28 (pp. 61-66). IEEE.
- [124] Greenspan M. Potential pitfalls of cognitive radars. In2014 IEEE Radar Conference 2014 May 19 (pp. 1288-1290). IEEE.
- [125] Piezzo M, De Maio A, Aubry A, Farina A. Cognitive radar waveform design for spectral coexistence. In2013 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarCon13) 2013 Apr 29 (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- [126] Howard WW, Martone AF, Buehrer RM. Distributed online learning for coexistence in cognitive radar networks. IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems. 2022 Aug 10.
- [127] Christiansen JM, Smith GE, Olsen KE. USRP based cognitive radar testbed. In2017 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarConf) 2017 May 8 (pp. 1115-1118). IEEE.
- [128] Wang J, Guan S, Jiang C, Alanis D, Ren Y, Hanzo L. Network association in machine-learning aided cognitive radar and communication co-design. IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications. 2019 Aug 16;37(10):2322-36.
- [129] La Manna M, Stinco P, Greco M, Gini F. Design of a cognitive radar for operation in spectrally dense environments. In2013 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarCon13) 2013 Apr 29 (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- [130] Güntürkün U. Toward the development of radar scene analyzer for cognitive radar. IEEE Journal of Oceanic Engineering. 2010 Apr 5;35(2):303-13.
- [131] Wicks M. Cognitive radar: A way forward. In2011 IEEE RadarCon (RADAR) 2011 May 23 (pp. 012-017). IEEE.
- [132] Bruggenwirth S. Design and implementation of a three-layer cognitive radar architecture. In2016 50th Asilomar Conference on Signals, Systems and Computers 2016 Nov 6 (pp. 929-933). IEEE.
- [133] Luo Y, Zhang Q, Hong W, Wu Y. Waveform design and high-resolution imaging of cognitive radar based on compressive sensing. Science China Information Sciences. 2012 Nov;55(11):2590-603.
- [134] Owen JW, Mohr CA, Kirk BH, Blunt SD, Martone AF, Sherbondy KD. Demonstration of real-time cognitive radar using spectrally-notched random FM waveforms. In2020 IEEE International Radar Conference (RADAR) 2020 Apr 28 (pp. 123-128). IEEE.
- [135] Elbir AM, Mulleti S, Cohen R, Fu R, Eldar YC. Deep-sparse array cognitive radar. In2019 13th International conference on Sampling Theory and Applications (SampTA) 2019 Jul 8 (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- [136] Cohen D, Dikopoltsev A, Ifraimov R, Eldar YC. Towards sub-Nyquist cognitive radar. In2016 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarConf) 2016 May 2 (pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- [137] Li X, Hu Z, Qiu R, Wu Z, Browning J, Wicks M. Demonstration of cognitive radar for target localization under interference. IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems. 2014 Oct;50(4):2440-55.
- [138] Chen P, Wu L. Waveform design for multiple extended targets in temporally correlated cognitive radar system. IET Radar, Sonar & Navigation. 2016 Feb;10(2):398-410.
- [139] Singerman PG, O'Rourke SM, Narayanan RM, Rangaswamy M. Language-based cost functions: Another step toward a truly cognitive radar. IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems. 2021 May 31;57(6):3827-43.
- [140] Hakobyan G, Armanious K, Yang B. Interference-aware cognitive radar: A remedy to the automotive interference problem. IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems. 2019 Oct 23;56(3):2326-39.
- [141] Karimi V, Mohseni R, Samadi S. Adaptive OFDM waveform design for cognitive radar in signal-dependent clutter. IEEE Systems Journal. 2019 Oct 14;14(3):3630-40.
- [142] Aubry A, Carotenuto V, De Maio A, Govoni MA, Farina A. Experimental analysis of block-sparsity-based spectrum sensing techniques for cognitive radar. IEEE Transactions on Aerospace and Electronic Systems. 2020 Sep 8;57(1):355-70.

- [143] Zhu M, Zhang Z, Li C, Li Y. JMRPE-Net: Joint modulation recognition and parameter estimation of cognitive radar signals with a deep multitask network. *IET Radar, Sonar & Navigation*. 2021 Nov;15(11):1508-24.
- [144] Tan QJ, Romero RA, Jenn DC. Target recognition with adaptive waveforms in cognitive radar using practical target RCS responses. In 2018 IEEE Radar Conference (RadarConf18) 2018 Apr 23 (pp. 0606-0611). IEEE.
- [145] Turlapaty A, Jin Y. Bayesian sequential parameter estimation by cognitive radar with multiantenna arrays. *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*. 2014 Dec 24;63(4):974-87.
- [146] Wei Y, Meng H, Liu Y, Wang X. Extended target recognition in cognitive radar networks. *Sensors*. 2010 Nov 11;10(11):10181-97.
- [147] Gurbuz AC, Mdrafi R, Cetiner BA. Cognitive radar target detection and tracking with multifunctional reconfigurable antennas. *IEEE Aerospace and electronic systems magazine*. 2020 Jun 1;35(6):64-76.
- [148] Romero RA, Goodman NA. Adaptive beam steering for search-and-track application with cognitive radar network. In 2011 IEEE Radar Con (RADAR) 2011 May 23 (pp. 1091-1095). IEEE.
- [149] Tang B, Tang J. Robust waveform design of wideband cognitive radar for extended target detection. In 2016 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP) 2016 Mar 20 (pp. 3096-3100). IEEE.
- [150] Nijssure Y, Chen Y, Rapajic P, Yuen C, Chew YH, Qin TF. Information-theoretic algorithm for waveform optimization within ultra wideband cognitive radar network. In 2010 IEEE International Conference on Ultra-Wideband 2010 Sep 20 (Vol. 2, pp. 1-4). IEEE.
- [151] Xue Y. Cognitive radar: theory and simulations. Reich GM, Antoniou M, Baker CJ. Memory-enhanced cognitive radar for autonomous navigation. *IET Radar, Sonar & Navigation*. 2020 Sep;14(9):1287-96.
- [152] Stinco P, Greco M, Gini F, La Manna M. Compressed spectrum sensing in cognitive radar systems. In 2014 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP) 2014 May 4 (pp. 81-85). IEEE.